

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING JUNIOR SCHOOL CHILDRENWORKS OF ART

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the development of a methodology for teaching fiction to younger schoolchildren. The purpose of the study is to develop an effective approach to the formation of literary competence in primary school children. The abstract provides an overview of the psychological and cognitive characteristics of younger schoolchildren, as well as current trends in the field of teaching literature at the initial stage of education. The methodology includes interactive forms of work, role-playing games, creative tasks and the use of modern educational technologies. The methodology was tested in literature lessons with the participation of younger schoolchildren, which revealed positive changes in their literary perception and analytical skills. In conclusion, the importance of the developed methodology for the formation of children's love of literature, the development of critical thinking and creative imagination at the initial stage of learning is emphasized.*

Keywords: *Teaching methods, Works of art, Literary competence, Interactive methods, Role-playing games, Creative tasks, Educational technologies, Literary perception, Critical thinking, Creative imagination, Psychology of primary school students.*

"We have identified the construction of the foundation of the Third Renaissance in our country as a strategic task and intend to raise it to the level of a national idea.

The systems of preschool, school, higher and secondary special education, scientific and cultural institutions are four interconnected links of the future Renaissance. We consider kindergarten teachers, school teachers, professors and teachers, scientific and creative intelligentsia to be the four most important pillars in shaping the era of the new Renaissance.

In this regard, we will act by harmonizing national experience with the best world achievements.

In a society where education and upbringing are developed, knowledge, culture and progress will necessarily prevail. Radicalism and extremism will never be able to take root in it.

We will consistently continue our work and do everything necessary to cover 80 percent of children with preschool education by 2025.

In addition, as part of the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, we have set ourselves the task of fully covering six-year-old children with a school preparation program by 2025," President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said.

Fiction plays an important role in the development of younger schoolchildren, contributing to the expansion of their horizons, the development of the emotional sphere and the formation of language skills. Well-organized teaching of works of art at primary school age can become the basis for further literary development and the formation of cultural competence of students.

Fiction plays an important role in the development of younger students, having a positive impact on their cognitive, emotional and social development. The following are the main aspects that highlight the role of fiction in the development of primary school children:

Language skills development: Reading fiction helps younger students expand their vocabulary, improve grammatical skills and develop speech. Interaction with a variety of texts

contributes to the formation of reading skills, understanding and interpretation of content, as well as develops expressive reading skills.

Developing Critical Thinking: Fiction allows younger students to analyze and evaluate texts, developing their critical thinking. Through comprehension of plots, characters and conflicts, students can form their point of view, argue their thoughts and express their own opinion.

Emotional development: Works of art help younger students develop emotional intelligence and understanding of other people's feelings. Through stories, characters and their experiences, students learn about different emotions and learn to empathize. Literature can help them realize and express their own emotions.

A specific method of teaching fiction to younger schoolchildren in Uzbek and Russian may include the following elements:

Introduction to the work: before starting to read the text, you can conduct an introductory lesson where students will get acquainted with the author, context and time of creation of the work. You can talk about the peculiarities of Uzbek and Russian literature, present concepts related to literary genres and styles.

Reading and text analysis: The teacher can read aloud or allow students to read individually. After reading, an analysis of the text follows, including a discussion of the plot, characters, basic ideas and symbols. You can ask questions that will help children make sense of what they have read and express their opinions.

Creative tasks: in order for students to actively participate in the learning process, they can be invited to complete creative tasks. For example, you can ask to write a continuation of the story, rewrite the events of the work in a modern context, or draw illustrations to the text. Such tasks develop the imagination, creative thinking and imagination of students.

Group projects: The organization of group projects can contribute to the development of social skills of younger students. Students can work in small groups to create their own theatrical productions based on the work they have read, have a discussion or play activities related to the plot of the work.

Finding similarities and differences: The methodology may also include a comparison of Uzbek and Russian fiction. Students can study the works of different authors and discuss similarities and differences in subjects, writing style, language use and cultural context features.

Practical tasks: The methodology may include practical tasks aimed at developing language skills. For example, students can compose their own stories, write poetry, or create mini-essays based on the works they have read.

It is important to take into account the age characteristics of younger students and adapt the methodology to their level of development and abilities. At the same time, the use of various methods and approaches to teaching fiction will help to include younger students in the learning and development process as effectively as possible.

Pedagogical approaches to teaching literature

Teaching literature is an important component of the educational process, which contributes to the development of language, communication and critical skills among students. Pedagogical approaches to teaching literature play a key role in the formation of interest in reading, understanding and analyzing literary works, as well as in the development of creative thinking and emotional intelligence among students.

In this part, we will look at several pedagogical approaches that help to conduct literature lessons effectively and interestingly. They include a variety of techniques, strategies and activities

that support the active participation of students and contribute to a deep understanding of literary texts.

The adaptation of methods to literature lessons requires taking into account the specific needs and interests of students, as well as their age characteristics. We will offer various approaches, including reading in groups, discussing texts, creative writing, role-playing, analyzing literary characters and creating your own works. These techniques will help to encourage students to actively participate, develop critical thinking and express their thoughts and feelings through literature.

Next, we will present some pedagogical approaches that contribute to the formation of analytical and creative skills in students, as well as the creation of an inspiring learning environment where literature becomes a source of pleasure and personal growth for each student.

The emergence of interest in literature and the development of reading and text comprehension skills are important tasks of primary school education. The method of teaching artistic works in primary school age should be adapted to the characteristics of children of this age group. Below are some features of teaching fiction at primary school age using the example of Uzbek and Russian languages:

A playful approach: At primary school age, children are especially responsive to playful forms of learning. Therefore, it is important to use game elements and activities when studying works of art. For example, you can conduct theatrical productions, role-playing games, creating puppet shows or drawing illustrations for works.

Visual support: Younger students remember information better when it is visually presented. Therefore, it is important to use illustrations, drawings and other visual tools that will help children better understand and remember the content of the works. You can show pictures, use multimedia materials, or organize the collective creation of illustrations.

Interactive methods: Younger students actively participate in learning when they are given opportunities for discussion and exchange of opinions. It is important to hold group discussions, include children in dialogues and give them the opportunity to express their thoughts and feelings about what they have read. You can also use the small group methodology, where each group will be responsible for studying a separate work and presenting their findings to the class.

Selection of literary works: When choosing works of art for younger students, it is necessary to take into account their interests and age characteristics. Literature should be accessible, contain vivid characters and interesting plots, and also correspond to the cultural context of children. It is important to provide a variety of types of works, such as fairy tales, poems, short stories, fairy tales of the peoples of Uzbekistan and Russia.

Language skills development: Teaching artistic works should contribute to the development of students' language skills. It is important to pay attention to the formation of vocabulary, understanding of basic literary terms and grammatical structures. You can conduct lexical games, create dictionaries of new words and phrases, as well as conduct exercises for reading aloud and expressive reading.

The study showed that teaching works of art using the example of Uzbek and Russian languages has its own characteristics. It is important to take into account cultural and historical contexts, as well as the diverse literary traditions and genres of each language. At the same time, the use of modern and accessible literary works allows you to make lessons more relevant and interesting for students.

Teaching artistic works is essential for the development of language skills, critical thinking, creativity and emotional intelligence in younger schoolchildren. A properly organized literature lesson can inspire students to read, allow them to discover the world of literature and expand their knowledge of culture and art.

In conclusion, I would like to note that an effective method of teaching artistic works to younger schoolchildren requires a flexible and individual approach to each student. It is important to create a learning environment where students can feel comfortable, express their thoughts and feelings, and develop their talents and abilities. The responsible role of a teacher is to become a mentor and inspiration for students, to help them reach their potential and become active readers and creative thinkers.

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